

cellular retinoic acid binding protein 1 (CRABP1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : CRABP1 is a cellular retinoic acid-binding protein, which is assumed to play an important role in retinoic acid-mediated differentiation and proliferation processes. The pleiotropic effects of retinoic acid (RA) in mammalian cells are mediated by two classes of proteins: the retinoic acid receptors (RAR) and CRABP-1/2. CRABP1 is known to be involved in multiple cancer proliferation pathways. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of CRABP1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of CRABP1 synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. cellular retinoic acid binding protein 1 (CRABP1)

A number of specific carrier proteins for members of the vitamin A family have been discovered. Two of these proteins bind all-trans-retinol and are found within cells important in vitamin A metabolism or function. Ong [14] observed that these two proteins had considerable sequence homology and named it cellular retinol-binding protein (CRBP) and cellular retinol-binding protein, type II (CRBP-II). A third intracellular protein, cellular retinoic acid-binding protein (CRABP, now CRABP1) was also observed to be structurally similar but bound only retinoic acid. Although retinol

appears to be bound quite similarly by the two retinol-binding proteins, they observed subtle differences related to the different functions of the two proteins. Further, coupled with the specific cellular locations of the two proteins, suggested their roles. Like CRBP, they observed that CRABP could deliver its ligand retinoic acid to specific binding sites within the nucleus (sites different from those for retinol). Thus, they hypothesized that the nuclear binding of retinol and retinoic acid might be a part of the mechanism by which vitamin A directs the state of differentiation of epithelial tissue.

Vaessen et al. [15] partially cloned and sequenced the human CRABP. van Kessel et al. [16] isolated a human genomic fragment comprising the CRABP gene and assigned it to human chromosome 15. They observed that CRABP mapped to the region 15q22-qter. Flagiello et al. [17] narrowed the assignment of CRABP1 to 15q24.

Retinoic acid (RA) is an important regulator of cell growth and differentiation both in fetal and in adult tissues. Two classes of proteins are involved in mediating the biological activities of RA. One of these, the retinoic acid receptors (RARs), encompasses ligand-inducible transcription factors that belong to the superfamily of nuclear hormone receptors (and specifically activated by RA). RARs associate with the retinoid X receptor (RXR) to form RAR/RXR heterodimers, which regulate transcription by binding to the polymorphic cis-acting response elements of RA target genes (Chambon [18]). The other class of intra-cellular proteins that bind RA with a high affinity comprises two homologous proteins, CRABP-1/2. The distinct patterns of expression of CRABP-1/2 suggest that they serve different functions in the biology of RA.

Dong et al. [19] showed that expression of CRABP-2, but not CRABP-1, markedly enhanced RAR-mediated transcriptional activation of a reporter gene in COS-7 cells. Their data suggested that transfer of RA from CRABP-1 to RAR involved dissociation of the ligand from the binding protein, followed by association with the receptor. In contrast, they observed that the movement of RA from CRABP-2 to the receptor was facilitated by a mechanism that involves direct interactions between CRABP-2 and RAR. Their findings revealed a striking functional difference between CRABP-1 and CRABP-2, and pointed at a novel mechanism by which the transcriptional activity of RA could be regulated by CRABP-2.

Michalik and Wahli [20] briefly discusses how retinoic acid signaling through RAR or PPAR- β/δ , depends on cytoplasmic retinoic acid transporters, which commits the cell to opposite fates, apoptosis or survival.

Leukemia-associated chimeric oncoproteins often act as transcriptional repressors, targeting promoters of master genes involved in hematopoiesis. Guidez et al. [21] showed that CRABP1 was a target of PLZF, which is fused to RAR α by the t(11;17)(q23;q21) translocation associated with RA-resistant acute promyelocytic leukemia (APL). They observed that PLZF repressed the CRABP1 locus and although the canonical, PLZF-RAR α oncoprotein had no impact on PLZF-mediated repression, the reciprocal translocation product RAR α -PLZF bound to this remote binding site, thus recruiting p300, and inducing promoter hypomethylation and CRABP-1 gene up-regulation. In line with these observations, they showed that RA-resistant murine PLZF/RAR α +RAR α /PLZF APL blasts expressed much higher levels of CRABP-1 than standard RA-sensitive PML/RAR α APL.

Meningiomas are the most common benign brain tumors. It has been observed that mutations of the E3 ubiquitin ligase TRAF7 occur in 25% of meningiomas and com-

monly co-occur with mutations in KLF4, yet the functional link between TRAF7 and KLF4 mutations remain unclear. By generating an in vitro meningioma model derived from primary meningeal cells, Najm et al. [22] elucidated the cooperative interactions that promote meningioma development. Their experiments indicated that the intricate molecular cross-talk between the ubiquitin ligase TRAF7 and the transcription factor KLF4 provided a first step toward the identification of new therapies for patients with meningioma. More specifically, the KLF4 target genes CRABP-2 was dysregulated in their datasets. Their RT-qPCR analysis confirmed the up-regulation of CRABP-2 by wt-KLF4 overexpression or TRAF7 suppression in human meningeal cells (HMCs).

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [23] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [24] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, •

linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [24].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [25]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [26], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance

based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [23] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [23]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [27], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the

projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. CRABP1 related synergies

Note - CRABP1 was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2^{nd} order combinations of CRABP1 were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [3] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Vasudevan et al. [3] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma and they also defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), cyclin

B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B) and Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of CRABP1 with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t CRABP1. CDCA5 - CRABP1 shows high ranking of ,161 (laplace) ,242 (linear) ,1 ,145 (jansen); and KIF18B - CRABP1 shows high ranking of ,206 (laplace) ,207 (linear) ,226 (rbf), 165 (jansen);

While, CKS2 - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,152 ,129 ,41 ,133; TPX2 - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,243 ,221 ,33 ,70; TOP2A - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,198 ,8 ,83 ,80; CCNB2 - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,55 ,5 ,56 ,252; TROAP - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,120 ,41 ,5 ,110; TK1 - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,109 ,28 ,195 ,220; BUB1B - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,224 ,59 ,40 ,95; CENPF - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,79 ,82 ,16 ,141; KIF4A - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,177 ,133 ,15 ,68; NEK2 - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,118 ,171 ,6 ,72; BRIP1 - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,70 ,73 ,54 ,210; DEPDC1B - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,67 ,97 ,115 ,8; and HJURP - CRABP1 shows low ranking of ,28 ,26 ,42 ,225.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t CRABP1 with CRABP1 – > CDCA5 / KIF18B.

3.1.2. CRABP1 unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by CRABP1, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. I document here, the 2nd order combinations with CRABP1, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the CRABP1 and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, ATPase Na⁺/K⁺ transporting subunit alpha 2 (ATP1A2), ST3 beta-galactoside alpha-2,3-sialyltransferase 6 (ST3GAL6), dehydrogenase/reductase 2 (DHRS2), anterior gradient 2, protein disulphide isomerase family member (AGR2), solute carrier family 16 member 6 (SLC16A6), non-SMC condensin I complex subunit G (NCAPG), solute carrier family 22 member 2 (SLC22A2), TTK protein kinase (TTK), centromere protein A (CENPA), gap junction protein alpha 3 (GJA3), prostate transmembrane protein, androgen induced 1 (PMEPA1), shugoshin 1 (SGO1), desmoglein 1 (DSG1), desmocollin 3 (DSC3), mitogen-activated protein kinase 4 (MAPK4), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), solute carrier family 22 member 8 (SLC22A8), solute carrier family 16 member 12 (SLC16A12), thymosin beta 15A (TMSB15A), solute carrier family 9 member C2 (putative) (SLC9C2), growth differentiation factor 9 (GDF9), chromatin licensing and DNA replication factor 1 (CDT1), PDZ binding kinase (PBK),

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CRABP1

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CRABP1				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - CRABP1	152	129	41	133
TPX2 - CRABP1	243	221	33	70
TOP2A - CRABP1	198	8	83	80
CCNB2 - CRABP1	55	5	56	252
CDCA5 - CRABP1	161	242	1	145
TROAP - CRABP1	120	41	5	110
TK1 - CRABP1	109	28	195	220
BUB1B - CRABP1	224	59	40	95
CENPF - CRABP1	79	82	16	141
KIF4A - CRABP1	177	133	15	68
NEK2 - CRABP1	118	171	6	72
KIF18B - CRABP1	206	207	226	165
BRIP1 - CRABP1	70	73	54	210
DEPDC1B - CRABP1	67	97	115	8
HJURP - CRABP1	28	26	42	225

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between CRABP1 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t CRABP1	
CDCA5	CRABP1
KIF18B	CRABP1

Table 2: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between CRABP1 and Individual members.

cytoskeleton associated protein 2 like (CKAP2L), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A regulatory beta subunit 3 (KCNAB3), cyclin dependent kinase 1 (CDK1), progesterin and adipoQ receptor family member 8 (PAQR8), establishment of sister chromatid cohesion N-acetyltransferase 2 (ESCO2), ribonucleotide reductase regulatory subunit M2 (RRM2), exonuclease 1 (EXO1), ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 C

(UBE2C), cyclin N-terminal domain containing 1 (CNTD1), zinc finger protein 114 (ZNF114), vomeronasal 1 receptor 1 (VN1R1), collagen type XVIII alpha 1 chain (COL18A1), H2B clustered histone 21 (HIST2H2BE), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), X-ray repair cross complementing 2 (XRCC2), spire type actin nucleation factor 2 (SPIRE2), SRRM2 antisense RNA 1 (SRRM2-AS1), mitochondrially encoded tRNA-Trp (UGA/G) (MT-TW), tripartite motif containing 59 (TRIM59), coiled-coil domain containing 183 (CCDC183), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 887 (LINC00887), reticulocalbin 1 pseudogene 2 (RCN1P2), MCM3AP antisense RNA 1 (MCM3AP-AS1), PITX1 antisense RNA 1 (C5orf66), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 954 (LINC00954), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A8, pseudogene (ANKRD20A8P), VIM antisense RNA 1 (VIM-AS1), deleted in lymphocytic leukemia 2 (DLEU2), NALCN antisense RNA 1 (NALCN-AS1), NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit B1 pseudogene 2 (NDUFB1P2), small regulatory polypeptide of amino acid response (SPAAR), CDKN2B and CDKN2A antisense cis and trans regulatory RNA 1 (CDKN2B-AS1), uroplakin 3B (UPK3B), RRS1 divergent transcript (RRS1-AS1), dynein axonemal heavy chain 10 opposite strand (DNAH10OS), family with sequence similarity 218 member A (FAM218A), and phosphoglycerate mutase 1 pseudogene 8 (PGAM1P8), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of CRABP1 with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t CRABP1.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t CRABP1 with CRABP1 – > RCN1 / PFKP / SCARB1 / CENPM / RNF32 / NCAPG / TTK / CENPF / KIF14 / PMEPA1 / HIF3A / CD101 / NAV1 / CEP55 / CILP / TICRR / NUF2 / CDCA5 / SLC16A12 / PLEKHG4B / CCDC144CP / HIST1H2BD / HIST1H4H / ZNF233 / CCDC78 / SLC9C2 / GPR146 / IGF2 / CDT1 / ESCO2 / ETV4 / CNTD1 / DNAJC22 / CA8 / HIST1H2AC / HIST1H2BC / NXPH4 / LINC01006 / COL18A1 / IGSF5 / HIST2H2BE / NDUFA4L2 / HIST1H1C / SMTNL2 / SLC38A3 / APOD / SLC30A10 / HCAR1 / MT-TW / TRIM59 / FIRRE / KLRK1 / LINC00887 / LCNL1 / C5orf66 / LINC00954 / ANKRD20A8P / DLEU2 / LINC01564 / SCARNA7 / UPK3B / RRS1-AS1 / HMGB1P21.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic CRABP1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of CRABP1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CRABP1									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CRABP1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ATP1A2 - CRABP1	1	238	176	169	ST3GAL6 - CRABP1	156	210	60	175
DHRS2 - CRABP1	12	162	135	209	AGR2 - CRABP1	2	245	224	243
SLC16A6 - CRABP1	51	232	163	251	NCAPG - CRABP1	251	134	51	204
SLC22A2 - CRABP1	3	166	161	226	TTK - CRABP1	171	204	30	207
CENPA - CRABP1	129	172	149	157	GJA3 - CRABP1	5	249	192	248
PMEPA1 - CRABP1	218	149	101	229	SGO1 - CRABP1	164	177	59	193
DSG1 - CRABP1	63	205	170	250	DSC3 - CRABP1	4	240	171	189
MAPK4 - CRABP1	8	178	173	246	CDCA5 - CRABP1	161	242	1	145
SLC22A8 - CRABP1	11	222	209	238	SLC16A12 - CRABP1	25	241	174	237
TMSB15A - CRABP1	139	231	24	216	SLC9C2 - CRABP1	56	219	148	159
GDF9 - CRABP1	199	196	69	195	CDT1 - CRABP1	153	201	221	228
PBK - CRABP1	195	161	245	79	CKAP2L - CRABP1	158	209	179	56
KCNAB3 - CRABP1	113	155	239	227	CDK1 - CRABP1	210	258	248	152
PAQR8 - CRABP1	38	236	242	202	ESCO2 - CRABP1	125	254	215	192
RRM2 - CRABP1	73	223	198	181	EXO1 - CRABP1	214	86	190	138
UBE2C - CRABP1	190	57	229	184	CNTD1 - CRABP1	146	248	256	200
ZNF114 - CRABP1	166	159	155	178	VN1R1 - CRABP1	20	244	201	191
COL18A1 - CRABP1	169	145	227	48	HIST2H2BE - CRABP1	211	235	196	18
KIF18B - CRABP1	206	207	226	165	XRCC2 - CRABP1	141	160	253	149
SPIRE2 - CRABP1	172	67	186	183	SRRM2-AS1 - CRABP1	200	197	133	25
MT-TW - CRABP1	247	156	249	60	TRIM59 - CRABP1	41	142	251	230
CCDC183 - CRABP1	219	243	160	217	LINC00887 - CRABP1	246	147	178	12
RCN1P2 - CRABP1	65	224	240	180	MCM3AP-AS1 - CRABP1	100	190	208	140
C5orf66 - CRABP1	36	174	222	249	LINC00954 - CRABP1	257	38	140	155
ANKRD20A8P - CRABP1	256	193	75	247	VIM-AS1 - CRABP1	114	184	235	176
DLEU2 - CRABP1	207	131	231	143	NALCN-AS1 - CRABP1	237	187	150	236
NDUFB1P2 - CRABP1	148	218	220	161	SPAAR - CRABP1	241	157	244	131
CDKN2B-AS1 - CRABP1	232	199	213	168	UPK3B - CRABP1	170	151	142	106
RRS1-AS1 - CRABP1	228	182	241	73	DNAH10OS - CRABP1	47	189	207	185
FAM218A - CRABP1	182	165	211	35	PGAM1P8 - CRABP1	99	239	194	196

Table 3: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between CRABP1 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t CRABP1	
ATP1A2 / ST3GAL6 / DHRS2 / AGR2 / SLC16A6 ...	
NCAPG / SLC22A2 / TTK / CENPA / GJA3 / PMEPA1 ...	
SGO1 / DSG1 / DSC3 / MAPK4 / CDCA5 / SLC22A8 ...	
SLC16A12 / TMSB15A / SLC9C2 / GDF9 / CDT1 ...	
PBK / CKAP2L / KCNAB3 / CDK1 / PAQR8 / ESCO2 ...	
RRM2 / EXO1 / UBE2C / CNTD1 / ZNF114 / VN1R1 ...	
COL18A1 / HIST2H2BE / KIF18B / XRCC2 / SPIRE2 ...	
SRRM2-AS1 / MT-TW / TRIM59 / CCDC183 / LINC00887 ...	
RCN1P2 / MCM3AP-AS1 / C5orf66 / LINC00954 / ...	
ANKRD20A8P / VIM-AS1 / DLEU2 / NALCN-AS1 / ...	
NDUFB1P2 / SPAAR / CDKN2B-AS1 / UPK3B / RRS1-AS1 ...	
DNAH10OS / FAM218A / PGAM1P8	

CRABP1

Table 4: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between CRABP1 and Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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